

Model-Based Analysis of Myocardial Strains in Obstructive and Non-Obstructive Hypertrophic Cardiomyopathy

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to propose preliminary results of a study focusing on an integrated cardiovascular model, including the left ventricular outflow tract obstruction (LVOT), to reproduce strain curves in obstructive and non-obstructive HCM patients. Clinical and echocardiography data were extracted from a database of 79 HCM patients enrolled in Rennes University Hospital. Unsupervised clustering was applied on a set of 12 clinical and echocardiography features per patient. Sensitivity analyses were performed to identify the most influential parameters on 6 outputs of the model. Two patients were selected, each associated with the centroid of the two defined clusters representing either a lower or higher proportion of obstructive patients. Then, two virtual patients were identified by adjusting manually model parameters to reproduce longitudinal strain curves as well as their LVOT pressure gradient. A close match was observed between simulated and experimental strains with a mean Root Mean Square Error of $3.75\% \pm 1.22$ for the C1 centroid (non-obstructive patient) and $3.96\% \pm 1.46$ for the C2 centroid (obstructive patient). This work demonstrated that the model was able to reproduce longitudinal strain curves and LVOT pressure gradient in both obstructive and non-obstructive HCM patients.

1. Introduction

Hypertrophic cardiomyopathy (HCM) is the most common heritable cardiovascular disease, with a reported prevalence of 0.2% (1:500) in the adult population [1]. HCM patients present a risk of sudden cardiac death (SCD) of 0.9% per year and it is the most common cause of SCD in young adults [2]. The complex and heterogeneous phenotype of HCM is characterized by increased left ventricular (LV) wall thickness, myocardial stiffness and impaired relaxation. Due to a thickened septum and anomalies of the mitral valve, HCM patients can also present an obstruction

of the LV outflow tract (LVOT) that could be associated with an increased risk of SCD [3].

Implantation of a cardioverter defibrillator (ICD) is a widely used therapy for treating patients at risk of SCD. Current guidelines and recommendations have been associated with low sensibility, especially for patients at intermediate risk, leading to undesirable effects [4, 5]. Therefore, it is clear that new predictors are needed to improve individual risk assessment in HCM patients.

Myocardial deformation is a highly multidimensional mechanism that allows the correct filling and ejection of the blood in the heart during one cardiac cycle. The longitudinal strain, which is the myocardial deformation along the long-axis, assessed by Speckle-Tracking Echocardiography, evaluates systolic function, and is especially relevant in HCM patients where the left ventricle ejection fraction (LVEF) is usually preserved despite impaired function. Therefore, strain seems to be a promising marker that could contribute positively to the current guidelines on risk assessment in HCM patients.

As it was mentioned, myocardial deformation includes several mechanisms which should be taken into account simultaneously when analyzing strain curves. In this regard, individual stratification of HCM could be improved by the use of computational models that integrate the mechanisms underlying myocardial deformation as well as physiological knowledge to facilitate the comprehension of strain curves. Our team has been actively working on the development of an integrated cardiovascular system model capable of computing myocardial strain curves [6, 7] by using a Multi-formalism Modeling and Simulation Library (M2SL) that we developed [8]. Additionally, in [9], a numerical model of ventricular outflow tract obstruction was developed. This model can be easily coupled with our integrated cardiovascular model to better represent the LVOT pressure gradient in HCM patients.

The objective of this paper is to propose preliminary results of this integrated cardiovascular model, including LVOT obstruction, in HCM patients.

2. Methods

2.1. Clinical and echocardiography data

The retrospective database includes 79 obstructive and non-obstructive HCM patients, enrolled in Rennes University Hospital, who underwent a 2D-speckle-tracking transthoracic echocardiography using a Vivid 7, E9, or E95 ultrasound system (GE Healthcare, Horten, Norway). Left ventricle longitudinal strain was obtained from apical 2-, 3- and 4- chamber views at a frame rate of at least 60 m/s (EchoPAC v204; GE Healthcare, Horten, Norway). The clinical data collected consisted of the echographic measurements, the 12-lead electrocardiograms and the exercise stress tests.

2.2. Unsupervised clustering for the identification of virtual patients

The K-Means method was applied on a set of 12 clinical features to define patient clusters using the scikit-learn library. These included the LVOT gradient during effort and rest, RR interval, E/A ratio, LVEF, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, maximal wall thickness, VO_2 peak, LV diastolic and systolic diameters and Global Longitudinal Strain (GLS). The number of clusters was set to two to obtain a group corresponding to the obstructive patients and a group corresponding to the non-obstructive patients. Then, the closest patient to each centroid, according to the Euclidean distance, was selected to reproduce the longitudinal strain through the integrated cardiovascular model. In order to visualize the clustering results, a principal component analysis (PCA) was performed.

2.3. Model description

The proposed model (Figure 1) was defined by coupling a representation of the LVOT to an integrated model of the cardiovascular system that includes: i) the cardiac electrical system, ii) the right and left atria, iii) the multi-segment right and left ventricles, iv) the systemic and pulmonary circulations and v) the heart valves. The model has been previously described in [7]. Each sub-model is briefly described as follows:

Cardiac Electric System: it is based on a set of coupled automata, adapted from [6].

Right and Left Atria: the mechanical function of the atria was modelled based on time varying elastance. Pressures in the right and left atria were defined as linear functions of their volumes intercepts and elastances.

Multi-Segment Right and Left Ventricles: the left ventricle was divided into 16 segments, according to the American Heart Association (AHA) recommendations, and the right ventricle into 3 segments. In each segment,

cardiac mechanic activity was described as the sum of active ($T_{s,a}$) and passive components ($T_{s,p}$). Both components were represented by non-linear equations that includes the $K_{s,act}$ and $K_{s,pass}$ parameters, which characterize myofiber contractility and passive stiffness, respectively. The complex electro-mechanical coupling was represented by an electro-mechanical driving function (EMDF) that is triggered by each automata in the ventricles.

Systemic and Pulmonary circulations: the model included the arteries, veins and capillaries of the pulmonary and systemic circulations. The blood flow was defined according to the difference of pressure across chambers and the vascular resistance. The pressure was defined based on an elastance model.

Heart valves: the four heart valves were modeled as perfect diodes. The model described in [9] was coupled at the level of sub-aortic valve (Figure 1):

$$Q = \sqrt{\frac{\Delta P_{obs}}{K_{obs}}} \quad (1)$$

$$K_{obs} = \frac{\rho}{2} * \left(\frac{1}{A_f} - \frac{1}{A} \right)^2 \quad (2)$$

where ΔP_{obs} is the difference of pressure between the left ventricle and the aorta, ρ is the blood density, A is the total aortic valve area and A_f is the effective area in the case of obstruction.

Figure 1. Cardiovascular model adapted from [7] and including LVOT obstruction. See [7] for more details.

2.4. Manual parameter estimation

Firstly, a sensitivity analysis was performed to identify the most influential parameters of the model. The methodology, based on Morris strategy, described in [7] was adapted for this analysis [10].

Parameters of the model were manually modified in order to simulate the strain curves. These modifications were based on the characteristic phenotype of HCM patients

Figure 2. **Middle:** K-means clusters: non-obstructive (blue) and obstructive (green) patients and its centroids (colored square). **Left:** patient-specific simulations results for the non-obstructive and, **Right:** the obstructive HCM patient; **upper:** experimental (black) and simulated (colored) strain curves corresponding to the 16 LV segments; **bottom left:** Aortic pressure (blue) and left ventricular pressure (green) showing the LVOT gradient; **bottom right:** Pressure-volume loop.

such as increased stiffness, increased or decreased contractility and impaired diastolic function. In addition, the novel parameter included in the model K_{obs} was adapted to simulate the resting LVOT gradient.

In order to quantify the error between the experimental and simulated curves, the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) was calculated for each segment s as follows:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{T} \sum_{t=0}^{T-1} (\epsilon_s^{exp}(t) - \epsilon_s^{sim}(t))^2} \quad (3)$$

where T is the heart period, $\epsilon_s^{exp}(t)$ and $\epsilon_s^{sim}(t)$ are the experimental and simulated curves, respectively.

3. Results

Clustering: Figure 2 in the middle shows the two clusters obtained, where C1 mostly represents the non-obstructive group (15% obstructive) and C2 had a greater proportion of obstructive patients (41% obstructive). The closest patients to each centroid were chosen for the simulation of strain curves. The experimental LVOT gradient was 6 mmHg and 31 mmHg for the non obstructive and obstructive patient, respectively.

Manual parameter estimation: Figure 2 shows a close match between simulated and clinical strains with a RMSE

averaged over segments equal to $3.75\% \pm 1.22$ for the C1 centroid (non obstructive patient) and $3.96\% \pm 1.46$ for the C2 centroid (obstructive patient). The obstructive patient showed a reduced strain, compared to a what is usually observed in healthy strain curves, in the mid-inferior, mid-inferior-septal, and mid-antero-septal segments, as well as in the apical-anterior and apical-lateral segments. On the contrary, the middle-anterior and basal-anterior segments seemed to have an hyper-deformation. Concerning the non-obstructive patient, the apical-anterior segment hardly deformed and the mid-inferior, mid-inferior-septal and mid-antero-septal segments showed an altered deformation related to a normal strain curve. Table 1 compares results between experimental and simulated data for the LVOT gradient and the GLS and close match was observed in both cases.

Table 1. Comparison between experimental (Exp.) and simulated (Sim.) data.

	RMSE (%)	LVOT gradient (mmHg)		GLS (%)	
		Exp.	Sim.	Exp.	Sim.
Obstructive Patient	3.96 (1.46)	31	31.66	-18.12	-18.64
Non Obstructive Patient	3.75 (1.22)	6	6.2	-16.31	-17.74

4. Discussion

In this work, a novel integrated model of the cardiovascular system was proposed to include LVOT obstruction. The model was able to reproduce experimental longitudinal strains as well as LVOT pressure gradient.

The integration of the LVOT obstruction is a first step in the development of more accurate and representative cardiovascular models in HCM as it allows to further understand how the increase in the resting pressure gradient might affect myocardial deformation. As we can see from Figure 2, decreased apical and septal myocardial deformation in the obstructive patient, with respect to what is usually observed in a healthy patient, would suggest an hypertrophy of these regions that would, at least partially, explain the obstruction of the LVOT. Furthermore, the distribution of the hypertrophy is in agreement with echocardiography data. On the other hand, hyper-deformation of others segments could be explained as a consequence of increased contractility as part of natural compensatory mechanisms in order to preserve the filling and ejection processes. Concerning the non-obstructive patient, apical anterior abnormal strain curve might be associated with a completely impaired diastolic function. Although septal hypertrophy was not observed from echocardiography images, septal segments showed a decreased deformation.

It is important to point out that both patients, representing the center patient of each cluster, presented abnormal deformation behaviour in septal segments. However, the mechanisms underlying altered myocardial deformation (in each center patient) are supposedly different. Obstruction of the LVOT is often associated with mitral valve structural anomalies and septum hypertrophy. Under the effect of flow drag during systole, the elongated leaflet blocks LVOT participating in the generation of the characteristic resting pressure gradient. On the other hand, the abnormal septal deformation observed in the non-obstructive patient might be a consequence of myocardial disarray, which could lead to increased wall thickness. Hence the interest in using integrated computational models to better understand myocardial deformation curves and the underlying mechanisms. In this model, heart valves were considered as perfect diodes. Therefore, this work does not account for possible structural changes in the mitral valve that could impact LVOT obstruction and mitral valve regurgitation. Additionally, our model makes some simplifications, such as not considering interaction between the left and right ventricles and simplifying the mechanics of contraction and relaxation. These aspects will be addressed in further developments of the model.

5. Conclusion

This work proposed a novel integrated model of the cardiovascular system that includes LVOT obstruction in

HCM patients. Our model reproduced experimental longitudinal strains as well as LVOT pressure gradient. Further work will concentrate in parameter identification algorithms to analyse larger databases as well as in incorporating mitral valve anomalies.

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